

Fathers' Involvement in Raising Children Aged 3–4 Years: Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Chad

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Abstract

The patriarchal structure of many African societies, in which responsibility for children's well-being lies predominantly with women, raises the question of fathers' participation in childrearing. This study examines the factors that facilitate or hinder fathers' involvement in raising children aged 3–4 years. To measure fathers' contribution to parenting, six activities were selected and grouped into two categories: cognitive and socio-emotional.

The study used data from the Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS) and included fathers aged 15–49 years whose children, aged 3–4 years, were living with them at the time of the survey. Chi-square tests and logistic regression analyses conducted on MICS data collected between 2014 and 2019 showed that only one-quarter of fathers contributed to the development of cognitive development, and one-third participated in children's socio-emotional activities.

Although child gender and mothers' attitudes and beliefs regarding gender roles and gender equality did not influence paternal support in the cognitive dimension, they were significantly associated with the socio-emotional dimension. In contrast, paternal polygamy and child age influenced cognitive support without affecting socio-emotional support. Country of residence, marital status, and education level were significantly associated with both categories of paternal support.

The findings suggest that national peace and security, marital status, and higher levels of education are associated with greater paternal investment in children's cognitive and socio-emotional development.

Keywords

parenting involvement, fatherhood, children, cognitive development, social-emotional development, Central Africa, MICS

JEL codes: I3, J12, J13

Introduction

Research on parenting has traditionally focused on mothers, describing their interactions with children and the impact of these interactions on children's development, while neglecting the role of fathers or generalizing to them findings obtained for mothers (Laflamme 2007). It was not until the 1970s that fathers, as active parents involved in childrearing, began to attract the attention of sociologists (Lamb 1975): initially through studies of time spent with children, and later through assessments of direct and indirect interactions with offspring. According to some authors (Rotundo 1985; Laflamme 2007), growing interest in paternal involvement research is linked to the gradual transformation of the father's role: from moral mentor and teacher to breadwinner and role model, and, in recent years, to that of a "maternal" or "androgynous" father who partially assumes caregiving responsibilities traditionally attributed to mothers. In the Western context, women's emancipation, their integration into the labour market, cultural diversification, and the rise in divorce and single-parent families are cited as drivers of these social changes. In Africa, however, paternal involvement remains insufficiently studied. Indeed, of the 37 empirical studies listed in the PsycNET database that examined determinants of paternal involvement with young children in intact families, twenty-eight were conducted in the United States, three in Canada, and only one in Africa – specifically in South Africa (Ross-Plourde et al. 2017).

However, research highlights the importance of fathers' involvement in their children's lives. In her study on parental support for ELE (*Éveil à la Lecture et à l'Écriture*, encouragement of early literacy practices), Breton (2018) emphasizes the need to promote fathers' involvement in order to positively influence children's development. Clinicians also report that fathers play an important role in the mother–infant separation stage, which enables the child to differentiate more clearly between the two parental figures. Through typically "masculine" play behaviours, such as up-and-down games, fathers symbolically support the child's separation from the mother (Lefebvre 2005). Fathers who are involved in their children's lives engage in shared activities and develop positive interactions, which contribute to reducing psychological distress and delinquent behaviour (Baker 2017; Brown et al. 2012; Kettani et al. 2017; Pruett et al. 2017). The father is also described as an authority figure, embodying law and order within the family structure (Le Camus 2000). According to Neyrand (1999), deficiencies in paternal parenting, associated with difficulties in maintaining a secure bond with children, are linked to maladjustment, delinquency, and other negative outcomes in later life.

Population growth rates in Africa provide an additional rationale for examining paternal involvement in childrearing in this region. The high number of children per woman – and consequently per man – raises questions about fathers' involvement in and investment in their children's development and well-being. This issue is particularly salient within the patriarchal context of many African societies, where domestic responsibilities, including the care of young children, are primarily assigned to women: "According to African traditions,

since women are the bearers of life, their primary roles are childbearing, maintaining the family hearth, and raising children” (Nkouma 2022: 6). A “good” mother is expected to provide for her children alongside her husband and to assume his role if he fails to do so (Adjagbo et al. 2005), whereas a mother perceived as neglecting her children may be exposed to domestic violence by her husband.

Although the importance of fathers at all stages of children’s lives – even before birth – is widely recognized, the human brain development curve (Thompson and Nelson 2001) indicates that the most rapid brain development occurs during the first 3–4 years of life (Grantham-McGregor et al. 2007). Most aspects of a child’s development (motor, socio-emotional, cognitive, and linguistic functions) take place before entry into primary school (Shonkoff 2010). These authors argue that the quality of parenting is the main factor determining children’s development during this period.

Cognitive and socio-emotional support are identified as two key dimensions of early learning: “By reading to children, telling them stories, pointing to objects, counting, and drawing with them, parents stimulate children’s curiosity and understanding of their environment, thereby promoting cognitive development. Socio-emotional activities – such as playing with children, singing, or going for walks together – help children feel valued and accepted; they foster emotional development, encourage appropriate behavioural responses, and provide a model of acceptable social relationships” (UNICEF 2012: 5–6).

It is within this framework that the present article analyses paternal support (cognitive and socio-emotional) in the upbringing of 3–4-year-old children in Cameroon, the Central African Republic (CAR), Congo, the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), and Chad.

Literature Review

In light of the documented benefits of paternal involvement for children, spouses, and fathers themselves (Pleck and Masciadrelli 2004), as well as ongoing transformations in family structures, numerous studies have examined the conditions that facilitate or hinder greater paternal engagement in children’s lives. Various instruments have been developed to measure paternal involvement, the most widely used being the multifactorial model proposed by Lamb et al. (1987).

Based on a factor analysis of 47 items measured on a 5–6-point Likert scale, Paquette et al. (2000) identified six dimensions of paternal involvement and assessed their internal consistency using Cronbach’s alpha: emotional support (12 items), openness to the world (9 items), basic care (9 items), physical play (7 items), stimulation (6 items), and discipline (4 items).

The UNICEF report (2012) on early childhood development highlights cognitive and socio-emotional support as critical dimensions of child development in the African context. Parents’ ability to care for their child and respond to their needs influences emotional and cognitive development, as well as social adjustment (Grossman et al. 2005; Lemelin et al. 2006; NICHD 2000; Feugé 2018).

These studies have given rise to various theoretical frameworks to explain differences in levels of paternal involvement. Attachment theory posits that when a parent is sensitive to a child’s distress and responds promptly and appropriately, the child is more likely to develop a secure attachment, which facilitates social and emotional adjustment (Bretherton 1985).

Several approaches within social representation theory have also been applied to the study of fatherhood. The perspectives developed by Doise (2003) and Abric (1987) emphasize the positions occupied by individuals and social groups, as well as the relationships and potential contradictions arising from these positions that regulate interpersonal and inter-group relations. According to these approaches, the level of paternal involvement is shaped both by individual factors (such as the father's personal history and childhood experiences, particularly his relationship with his own father) and by the broader social and ideological system in which he is embedded, including the nature of his ties to that system.

Family systems theory argues against isolating the father–child dyad and instead recommends considering the mother–child and parent–parent dyads, as well as the father–mother–child triad, when analysing paternal involvement. This perspective advocates integrating characteristics of mothers, children, and the family context to better understand fathers' participation in activities that promote children's development.

Activation relationship theory posits that fathers play a distinct role in the parent–child relationship. They are more involved in the child's exploration and discovery of the world, whereas mothers provide security and comfort. This perspective supports the idea of a gender-based division of domestic roles: fathers stimulate and engage in play, while mothers soothe and reassure (Lamb 1996). According to the theory of planned behaviour, paternal involvement reflects an individual's beliefs and values regarding fatherhood, particularly those shaped by his relationship with his own father during childhood.

The ecological model proposed by Turcotte and Gaudet (2009) (see Figure A1 in the Appendix) identifies multiple factors that may influence paternal involvement. It conceptualizes fatherhood as a dynamic, bidirectional process resulting from interactions among the individual (with his personality traits, attitudes, behaviours, and social background), his family (spouse and children), and the broader environment, as well as societal expectations regarding child development (Diniz et al. 2021).

Various paternal characteristics have been examined to explain differences in involvement, including the relationship with one's own father during childhood, attitudes and beliefs about gender roles, personality traits, perceived parental competence, age, and social status. With some exceptions, the paternal role model experienced in childhood appears to significantly influence men's involvement with their own children (Feldman et al. 1983; Gerson 1993), although the direction of this relationship remains unclear. Studies using *Bem's Sex Role Inventory* – a questionnaire measuring gender identity¹ – have shown that fathers with androgynous personality traits² are more likely to engage in caregiving and interactive activities with their children than those who adhere exclusively to traditional masculine norms (Lamb et al. 1987; Russell 1982; Bird et al. 1984; Radin 1981).

Given the gender division of labour in many African contexts, which assigns primary responsibility for household tasks – including childcare – to women, domestic violence perpetrated by fathers in response to a mother's perceived inadequate care of children may reflect traditional attitudes toward childrearing. Such attitudes are generally considered to be negatively correlated with paternal involvement.

The work of Mash and Johnston (1983) conceptualizes parental competence in terms of perceived effectiveness in parenting development and satisfaction with one's parental role. A study conducted in 2000 by the NICHD (National Institute of Child Health and Human

1 An instrument widely used to measure gender role perceptions (Holt and Ellis 1998).

2 Combination of feminine and masculine character traits.

Development) found a significant effect of fathers' age on paternal involvement; however, the association varied depending on the dimension considered. Younger fathers were more involved in caregiving activities, whereas older fathers were more engaged in interactive activities with their children. Similarly, Coltrane (1995) suggests that paternal involvement tends to increase with age.

Because the father–child dyad does not function in isolation within the family system, maternal characteristics have increasingly been examined as predictors of paternal involvement. The role of “gatekeeper” is often attributed to the mother, who may regulate fathers' participation in their children's lives (Turcotte and Gaudet 2009). Research (Barnett and Baruch 1987; Feldman et al. 1983; Palkovitz 1984; Starrels 1994) indicates that certain maternal characteristics – such as attitudes and beliefs regarding gender roles, labour market participation, and informal power within the household – may be more influential in predicting paternal involvement than fathers' own characteristics.

In the case of fathers, traditional attitudes toward gender roles are associated with the risk of domestic violence linked to child neglect. The influence of formal and informal power within a couple on paternal involvement has been examined primarily in terms of differences in resources, such as income and social prestige, between spouses. Findings generally indicate that the more comparable the parents' incomes, the more likely fathers are to participate in childcare (Steil and Turetsky 1987; Deutsch et al. 1993; Starrels 1994).

Other indicators of formal and informal power within the family have also been considered. Among these is the age difference between spouses, which has been identified as a factor influencing women's decision-making autonomy in Chad (Tagang and Rwenge 2023). These authors note that women who are substantially younger than their husbands – by at least ten years – are less likely to exercise independent decision-making. Although men are generally older than women in heterosexual couples, the magnitude of the age gap varies (Bergström 2018), and sub-Saharan Africa exhibits some of the largest spousal age differences globally (Barbieri and Hertrich 2005).

The number, temperament, age, and gender of children are identified as among the most stable predictors of paternal involvement (Marsiglio 1991). Regarding the first characteristic, “fathers with higher levels of involvement are more likely to be found in families with a large number of young children, although larger family size may actually lead to lower levels of involvement in some activities because children will have a greater choice of play-mates” (Marsiglio 1991: 976).

Some authors (Volling and Belsky 1991; Woodworth et al. 1996) were unable to establish a relationship between the child's temperament and paternal involvement, while others (Simons et al. 1990; McBride et al. 2002) argue that perceiving a child as “difficult” negatively affects paternal engagement. In contrast, the negative correlation between the child's age and paternal involvement is widely accepted. Research (Cooksey and Fondel 1996; Russell 1982; Marsiglio 1991; Hofferth 2003) indicates that fathers are more involved with younger children, particularly in activities such as reading, playing, and recreational interaction.

The relationship between child gender and paternal involvement is more complex. Some studies suggest that fathers interact more frequently with young sons (Barnett and Baruch 1987; Cooksey and Fondel 1996; Harris and Morgan 1991; Marsiglio 1991; Starrels 1994; Manlove and Vernon-Feagans 2002) and with adolescents of both sexes, than with young daughters (Pleck and Hofferth 2008). However, the effect of child gender appears to be mediated by the gender composition of siblings (Cooksey and Fondel 1996; Harris and Morgan 1991; Marsiglio 1991). These studies found that (1) the highest levels of paternal involve-

ment occur in families where all children are boys, and (2) the more brothers a father has, the more likely he is to maintain stimulating, affectionate, and warm relationships with his daughters. Other studies (Grossman et al. 1988; Radin and Harold-Goldsmith 1989; Snarey 1993) report that child gender does not significantly affect paternal involvement.

When studying child development, it is important to evaluate not only parent–child interactions but also parent–parent interactions and the potential indirect ways in which the family system may influence the child (Planalp and Braungart-Rieker 2016). Marital conflict has been shown to negatively affect father–child interactions (Volling and Belsky 1991) and to reduce paternal involvement in parenting (Easterbrooks et al. 2014).

Various instruments have been used to assess the quality of marital relationships, including the Locke-Wallace Marital Adjustment Scale³ (Paquette et al. 2000), the Braker and Kelly Four-Factor Intimate Relationships Scale (Volling and Belsky 1991), and the Parenting Alliance Inventory⁴ (Gagnon 2012). The type of marital union is also considered a factor influencing relationship quality. Cohabiting unions tend to be less stable than formal marriages (Burch and Madan 1986; Le Bourdais et al. 2000), and families that begin with cohabitation are generally less stable than those that begin directly with formal marriage (Le Bourdais et al. 2000).

Although marital relationships in Africa often remain unequal (Dabo 2017), legal recognition of the union provides greater stability and is associated with higher levels of paternal involvement in childrearing. The parenting behaviour of single fathers is often more similar to that of mothers than to married fathers (Risman 1987). Separated or divorced mothers who report high levels of satisfaction with their own parents' support are generally more open to fathers' involvement in parenting and report fewer conflicts with them (Herzog et al. 2007; Kulik and Tsoref 2010; Ganong et al. 2012).

In Central Africa in general, and in the countries studied (Cameroon, CAR, Congo, DR Congo, and Chad), two forms of marriage are prevalent: monogamy and polygamy, and marital relations differ substantially between these forms. Polygamous families often experience numerous conflicts, including those between co-wives, between children from different wives, and between a wife and her children versus the husband and his other wives and children (Leonard 2014). Children in polygamous families are at higher risk of physical and psychological abuse, as they may be affected by rivalry among the father's wives. Additionally, having a large number of children in the family may result in less time spent with parents and reduced attention and supervision from the father (Elbedour et al. 2000, 2003a, 2003b; Strassmann 1997).

Polygyny may also manifest as multiple sexual relationships, particularly when practiced outside legal recognition.

Methodology and data sources

The Prospère team selected 47 items to measure the father–child relationship and identified six dimensions of paternal involvement as presented in the literature. To analyse fatherhood as a form of support for early childhood care, we used six items selected by UNICEF from the Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS). These items include: reading books

3 The Locke Adaptation Test is based on an integral indicator obtained from 50 indicators measuring the success of marriage (Locke and Wallace 1959).

4 The concept of the questionnaire was developed by Weissman and Cohen (Weissman and Cohen 1985).

or looking at picture books, telling stories, singing, walking, playing games, and counting or drawing. Each item had two possible responses: “yes,” if the father had participated in the activity within the last three days, and “no,” if he had not.

Cramer’s V was used to measure the strength of association between pairs of activities, and Cronbach’s alpha was applied to assess internal consistency within paternal support for childrearing. Using data from the 2014 Cameroon, 2014–15 Congo, 2017–18 DR Congo, 2018–19 CAR, and 2019 Chad MICS surveys, we estimated associations between these items (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Strength of association between activities in the father–child dyad. *Source:* calculated by the author based on MICS survey data

The strongest association (Cramer’s $V = 0.41$) was observed between the activities “storytelling” and “singing.” Of the six dimensions of paternal involvement identified by Paquette et al. (2000), these two activities correspond to emotional support, represented by twelve items; they characterize parental behaviours that clearly communicate to the child that he or she is valued, loved, supported, and protected. Given the theoretical link between physical play, novelty, and discipline activities, Vandystadt (2017) combined these three dimensions to create a measure of paternal involvement in promoting openness to the world.

Reading was primarily associated with drawing and counting ($V = 0.39$), as well as with storytelling ($V = 0.31$). Through these activities, fathers teach children age-appropriate behaviours and contribute to the development of their cognitive development. Participation in these activities is therefore considered supportive of cognitive development. Paquette

et al. (2000) note that “the four-item Discipline section addressed parental actions aimed at correcting the child’s behaviour or teaching age-appropriate behaviour.” The authors obtained a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.75 for the internal consistency of this measure, compared with 0.56 in our estimates.

Walking was mostly correlated with playing with children ($V = 0.35$) and singing ($V = 0.33$). These activities aim to encourage the child and introduce them to new experiences, thereby fostering openness to the world (David 2017; Paquette et al. 2000). They are incorporated into the dimension of openness to the world, which combines emotional support and exposure to novelty. In our study, the Cronbach’s alpha for this measure was 0.56, similar to the value reported for reading.

According to the literature on fathers’ involvement with children aged 3–4 years, factors influencing the father–child relationship include child gender and age, marital status, type of marriage or partnership, father’s education level, parental beliefs regarding gender roles, number of children in the household, father’s age, age difference between parents, and household financial stability.

To obtain comprehensive information about children and their parents, the study included all men living with at least one child aged 3–4 years and with the mothers of these children. The total sample size was 5,030 men, distributed as follows: 1,614 in Chad, 1,270 in DR Congo, 770 in CAR, 756 in Congo, and 620 in Cameroon. The characteristics of the sample are presented in Table A1 in the Appendix.

In the sample studied, children were distributed almost equally by gender. With the exception of Congo, where boys outnumber girls, girls constitute the majority in the other countries, while in the Central African Republic the numbers of boys and girls are equal. Child age was also considered a factor influencing paternal involvement, with children divided into two groups: three and four years old. This characteristic was similarly balanced across the countries studied.

The quality of the marital relationship between parents was assessed using two factors: marital status and number of sexual partners. Marital status distinguished men in informal unions at the time of the survey from those who were legally married. Civil unions predominated in the Central African Republic, whereas formal marriage was more common in the other countries, and in Chad nearly all fathers (99%) were legally married.

The number of sexual partners serves as an indicator of sexual behaviour and, to some extent, polygamy. The data show that multiple sexual relationships are most common in Chad, where approximately one-quarter of men report them, compared with around two-fifths in the Central African Republic and 15% in the other countries.

Fathers’ education levels are lowest in Chad and the Central African Republic, with only one in ten fathers having completed secondary school. In contrast, education levels are higher in Congo and DR Congo, where more than half of fathers have attained secondary education.

Parental (both father and mother) views and beliefs regarding gender roles are related to spousal abuse arising from child neglect. Many parents hold traditional beliefs, considering it acceptable for a husband to hit or beat his wife if she neglects her maternal duties. This traditional attitude is widespread in the Central African countries studied. In Cameroon and Congo, the majority of mothers adhere to traditional views (66.9% and 51.2%, respectively). In the Central African Republic and the Democratic Republic of Congo, more than 40% of mothers justify violence against themselves in cases of child neglect, whereas in Chad nearly two-thirds of wives oppose such violence.

Compared with mothers, fathers are generally more opposed to violence in the Central African Republic, Congo, and the Democratic Republic of Congo, with approximately three in ten men in these countries rejecting the traditional position. In Cameroon, however, the high proportion of mothers with traditional views is accompanied by the highest proportion of fathers holding similar views among the countries studied, with more than one-quarter justifying domestic violence as a consequence of maternal neglect of children.

In each of the countries studied, the majority of the sample consisted of fathers aged 30 to 39 years: over half in Cameroon (53.2%) and DR Congo (52.4%), while in the remaining countries their proportion was slightly below the average.

The age difference between spouses was used as an indicator of informal power within the couple and was divided into three categories: less than 5 years, 5 to 10 years, and 10 years or more. The first category predominated in the Central African Republic and Congo, accounting for over 40% of the sample in each country. In the other countries, the most common age gap was 5–9 years, reported by 40% of respondents in DR Congo and Chad. In Cameroon, the distribution among the three categories was relatively even, while the overall age gap was highest in Chad, where more than one-third of fathers were 10 or more years older than their wives.

Household living standards were used to assess the financial stability of fathers and their environment. Fathers living in low-income households were the majority in DR Congo and Chad, representing three out of five fathers in the sample from these countries. In the other countries, financially disadvantaged fathers constituted a minority, accounting for approximately 40% of the sample in each country.

Results and discussion

There is very limited literature on the relationship between macro-level human development indicators and paternal involvement in childrearing. Most existing studies focus on the influence of individual and family characteristics on fathers' engagement in their children's lives.

Figure 2 presents the proportion of fathers involved in early childhood care, by type of skill and country of residence. Overall paternal involvement is highest in Congo, where more than half of fathers (52%) report participation in parenting activities, and lowest in the Central African Republic (approximately 38%). This pattern suggests that the Human Development Index (HDI) may be one of the contextual factors associated with paternal involvement. In 2017, the HDI was highest in Congo (0.606) and lowest in the Central African Republic (0.367) (UNDP 2018).

The residuals from the chi-square test indicate that Cameroon, DR Congo, and Chad occupy intermediate positions, with more than 40% of fathers involved in childrearing. This distribution broadly corresponds to their intermediate ranking in the HDI among the five countries studied. Moreover, this hierarchy of paternal involvement partially aligns with the overall level of developmental support available to children in these countries.

Regarding the development of children's socio-emotional development, paternal involvement is again highest in Congo, where nearly 50% of fathers report engagement in such activities. The chi-square test confirms that this rate is significantly higher than in the other countries. In contrast, fathers in the Central African Republic (30%) and Chad (32%) are less involved in socio-emotional support. Cameroon and DR Congo display in-

intermediate levels of paternal involvement in socio-emotional development (34% and 37%, respectively).

However, two findings challenge the straightforward use of HDI as a classificatory framework for paternal involvement. First, the high level of fathers' contribution to children's cognitive development in Congo (HDI = 0.606, the highest among the five countries) does not differ significantly from that observed in Chad (HDI = 0.404). Second, Cameroon (HDI = 0.556) exhibits the lowest level of cognitive support (20%), compared with 24% in the Central African Republic (HDI = 0.367) and DR Congo (HDI = 0.457).

Figure 2. Proportion of fathers involved in childrearing, by country and skill type. *Source:* calculated by the author based on MICS survey data

The results of the binary logistic regression models used to identify facilitators and barriers to paternal involvement are presented in Tables A2 and A3 in the Appendix. The predictive accuracy of the models is highest for cognitive support (73.6%) and lowest for the overall measure of paternal involvement (57.6%).

Fathers' levels of involvement vary according to several paternal characteristics, and these characteristics operate differently across the various dimensions of involvement. This variation underscores the importance of distinguishing between types of paternal involvement

when analysing determinants of father–child engagement. Some factors – such as country of residence, father’s level of education, and marital status – are significant across all types of involvement, whereas others exert differential effects depending on the specific dimension considered.

a) Invariants of fathers’ involvement in parenting

Congo exhibits the highest levels of paternal involvement in both cognitive activities (76% higher odds than in Cameroon) and socio-emotional activities (59% higher odds than in the other countries), and, accordingly, the highest overall level of paternal involvement (approximately 50% higher odds than in the other countries). This pattern may be explained by comparatively more favourable living conditions in Congo. Unlike the other countries studied, Congo has not experienced major armed conflicts in recent years. By contrast, cross-border violence in the Lake Chad Basin associated with Boko Haram, electoral unrest in the Democratic Republic of Congo, military and political crises in the Central African Republic, and the Anglophone crisis in Cameroon have increased psychological stress and tension among parents, thereby heightening the risk of hostile parenting behaviours, including aggressive tones of voice, belittlement, and persistent harsh criticism (Elder et al. 1992; Turcotte et al. 2001). According to the Global Terrorism Index published by the Institute for Economics and Peace (IEP 2020), Cameroon ranks highest among the countries studied (7.0), followed by the Democratic Republic of Congo (6.6), the Central African Republic (6.52), Chad (4.83), and Congo (2.04). Higher exposure to insecurity in countries such as Cameroon and the Democratic Republic of Congo may increase fathers’ vulnerability to anxiety and psychological stress, which in turn may negatively affect their interactions with their children.

Higher levels of paternal education are positively associated with participation in activities that stimulate children’s cognitive development. Fathers with lower secondary education have 25% higher odds of supporting their child’s cognitive development in early childhood, while those with upper secondary education have 18% higher odds, compared with fathers with no education. These differences may reflect disparities in knowledge, development, and the capacity to transfer them to children. Fathers with basic education are likely to demonstrate greater proficiency in reading, numeracy, and drawing than those with no schooling, whereas fathers with upper secondary education or higher may be more aware of the importance of early cognitive stimulation and better equipped to support it. Time spent in education may also enhance fathers’ understanding of their children’s academic progress and the importance of cognitive engagement (Yeung et al. 2001; Marsiglio 1991). In addition, fathers who did not complete secondary education had 18% lower odds of participating in walks and games with their children. However, a study of families in the United States conducted by Hofferth (2003) did not find a significant association between fathers’ educational level and their involvement in childrearing. This discrepancy may be explained by the higher overall educational attainment of fathers in that sample (expected years of schooling: 13.28) compared with the present study. In our analysis, the association is statistically significant only in the Democratic Republic of Congo and Cameroon, with larger differences observed in Cameroon. In Cameroon, fathers who have completed upper secondary education have approximately twice the odds of being involved in childrearing. This result may be related to the relatively higher expected years of schooling in Cameroon (13 years) (UNESCO).

Marital status is positively associated with several forms of paternal involvement. Fathers who are legally married have 60% higher odds of engaging in cognitively stimulating activ-

ities (reading, storytelling, arithmetic, and drawing) and 21% higher odds of participating in play, singing, and walks with their child compared with fathers in informal unions. Greater involvement in cognitive activities may indicate a stronger orientation toward children's academic development. Legal marriage may be associated with more stable spousal interaction, in which partners share a common vision of family life and participate more actively in joint activities, both domestic and parental. Such shared understanding between spouses may facilitate greater paternal involvement in childrearing (McBride and Rane 1998). Previous research (Burch and Madan 1986; Le Bourdais et al. 2000) suggests that civil unions tend to be less stable than formal marriages. These findings differ from those of Risman (1987), who reported lower involvement among married fathers. One possible explanation for this discrepancy is that the association between union type and paternal involvement reflects differences in the gender division of labour rather than marital quality per se. In formally institutionalized marriages, traditional role differentiation may structure parental responsibilities in ways that limit fathers' engagement, whereas in informal unions parental roles may be more egalitarian. Thus, the effect of marital status reported in the literature may be more closely related to the gender division of labour than to the intrinsic quality of the marital relationship.

b) Types of paternal involvement

Some characteristics are significantly associated with one type of paternal involvement but not with another. These include the child's gender and age, parents' beliefs and attitudes toward gender roles, number of sexual partners, gender equality within the couple, father's age, age difference between spouses, and financial instability.

Child gender is significantly associated with the development of social-emotional development. Fathers of boys have 36% higher odds of engaging in activities such as walking, singing, and playing with their children. Fathers tend to interact more with sons because they feel better prepared and more comfortable engaging with boys (Harris and Morgan 1991; Cooksey and Fondell 1996; Yeung et al. 2001). Their own childhood experiences may enable them to better understand the expectations and interests of their sons, who, unlike daughters, may encourage participation in gender-typed activities such as playing ball. However, child gender is not significantly associated with paternal involvement in cognitively stimulating activities related to school achievement.

Fathers are equally involved in cognitive activities with sons and daughters, suggesting equal opportunities for academic support. Indeed, MICS survey reports from these Central African countries do not reveal substantial gender differences in enrolment in pre-primary education (officially for children aged 3–5). Hofferth (2003) reports different findings, which may reflect more egalitarian gender relations in American families. Thus, although fathers may prefer the father–son dyad in leisure activities, they provide children of both sexes with comparable cognitive support.

With the exception of Chad and Congo, child gender is significantly associated with overall paternal involvement. Gender inequality and adverse living conditions may explain this pattern in Cameroon, the Central African Republic (CAR), and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). In contexts of low human development and female marginalization, fathers may prioritize relationships within the father–son dyad.

A father's non-traditional attitudes toward gender-role distribution increase the likelihood of his overall involvement in childrearing, without affecting specific types of activity. Men who justify domestic violence in cases of perceived maternal neglect have 15% lower odds of being involved in childrearing. Such attitudes may reflect the transfer of responsi-

bility for parenting to mothers. According to psychological distress theory, aggressive men may experience difficulties with emotional regulation, which contradicts core parenting values such as empathy and respect for dignity (Welbes and Reuter 2006). Although maternal non-involvement may not always be perceived as neglect, spousal violence associated with child-related conflicts reduces overall paternal engagement.

Mothers' non-traditional gender attitudes positively influence fathers' involvement in social-emotional activities. Mothers' rejection of domestic violence increases fathers' odds of engaging in play, walking, or singing by 14%, but does not affect cognitive involvement. This suggests that mothers perceive childrearing primarily in terms of organizing leisure activities. In many Central African contexts, women traditionally exercise influence within the family sphere, particularly in interactions with children (Pleck 1983), often through socio-emotional engagement.

While fathers' beliefs are not linked to specific types of activities, mothers' attitudes are associated primarily with socio-emotional involvement. This reflects a division of parental roles in which mothers are more closely associated with nurturing and emotional security. In Chad and the CAR – countries with higher levels of gender inequality – parental attitudes show stronger associations with paternal involvement. High tolerance of domestic violence in these contexts corresponds with lower paternal engagement, consistent with findings that violent marital relationships undermine father–child interaction (Bancroft et al. 2002; Bourassa et al. 2008; Holden and Barker 2004; Peled 1998).

The number of sexual partners – an indicator of marital structure – is negatively associated with children's cognitive development. Children whose fathers have multiple wives have 19% lower odds of receiving cognitive support. Fathers in polygynous families may limit such involvement to avoid perceptions of favoritism, a known source of intra-household tension (Leonard 2014). No significant association was observed for socio-emotional support. In Chad, where polygyny is more widespread, fathers with at least two wives have 36% lower odds of being involved in childrearing. The absence of similar effects in other countries suggests that it is polygyny specifically, rather than multiple partnerships per se, that constrains paternal involvement.

The number of children is negatively associated with socio-emotional involvement. Fathers in larger families have lower odds of engaging in activities such as singing, playing, or walking with children. Organizing leisure activities for multiple children increases both logistical complexity and financial costs. The association becomes statistically significant from three children onward and is observed only in Cameroon, where fathers with three or more children have 36% lower odds of engagement. This contrasts with some prior findings (Marsiglio 1991), possibly reflecting the interaction between family size and polygyny in the Central African context.

Child age positively affects paternal involvement in cognitive activities. Four-year-olds have 15% higher odds of receiving support in reading and arithmetic compared with three-year-olds. This may reflect greater enrolment in preschool and increased academic demands. No significant association was found between child age and socio-emotional or overall involvement. The narrow age range (3–4 years) may limit observable variation.

Consistent with Marsiglio (1991), father's age is not significantly associated with paternal involvement. Similarly, age differences between spouses and household financial instability are not significant predictors at the regional level. However, in Cameroon, fathers over 40 whose age difference with their spouse does not exceed four years demonstrate lower involvement, possibly reflecting generational shifts in parenting norms.

In Chad, household financial insecurity reduces the odds of paternal involvement by 22%. Given the high prevalence of multidimensional poverty in the country (UNDP 2018), economic vulnerability may increase psychological distress and constrain fathers' capacity to engage in parenting (Harris et al. 1998; Leinonen et al. 2002).

Conclusion

This article examines paternal involvement in the upbringing of 3–4-year-old children in selected Central African countries, with the aim of identifying factors that facilitate or hinder such involvement. To measure fathers' participation in parenting, six activities were selected and divided into two subcategories: cognitive and socio-emotional support. Analysis of the internal correlations among these activities showed that, except for singing and storytelling, associations were stronger within the same subcategory. The strong correlation between singing and storytelling is justified because both relate to socio-affective, emotional support, through which fathers communicate to their children that they are valued, loved, supported, and protected (Paquette et al. 2000).

Cognitive support, measured through activities such as reading, storytelling, arithmetic, and drawing, was relatively low, with only about a quarter of fathers participating in at least one of these activities. In contrast, participation in social-emotional activities – playing with children, singing, or going for walks – was higher, with roughly one-third of fathers demonstrating this type of support. Correlation analysis indicates a strong connection between storytelling (cognitive) and singing (social-emotional), suggesting some overlap between these two dimensions of paternal involvement.

At the sub-regional level, three regression models were constructed, one for each category of paternal involvement. The overall involvement model, with a predictive power of 57.6%, identified country of residence, child's gender, marital status, multiple sexual partners, education level, and parents' attitudes and beliefs about gender roles as significant determinants. In Congo, fathers were more involved with their sons if they were in formal marriages, had a single spouse, were better educated, and held non-traditional views on gender roles.

Barriers to paternal involvement include lack of security, polygamy or multiple sexual partners, domestic violence, low or no education, and gendered divisions of parental roles, while facilitators include formal marriage, higher education, and peaceful living conditions. These factors vary by type of involvement, allowing the identification of distinct patterns in fathers' participation.

Child gender, mothers' attitudes and beliefs about gender roles, and the number of children did not influence cognitive development but were significantly associated with socio-emotional development. This difference can be explained by: (1) fathers' personal childhood experiences and engagement in gendered activities, which affect socio-emotional development more in boys, while cognitive development are less gender-dependent; (2) mothers' involvement in parenting being mainly leisure-oriented, consistent with the activation relationship theory, which links maternal roles to security; and (3) the challenges of organizing leisure activities for multiple children, as well as the financial resources required, which reduce fathers' socio-emotional support in larger families.

Conversely, the number of marital partners and child age influenced cognitive development without significantly affecting socio-emotional development. This can be explained by (1) the high costs of pre-primary education in polygamous families with many children,

and (2) the higher enrolment of 4-year-olds in pre-primary programmes, which increases the need for cognitive support from fathers.

Country of residence, marital status, and fathers' education remain significant correlates across both categories of involvement, representing invariants of paternal participation. In Central Africa, peaceful environments, formal marriage, and higher education facilitate fathers' engagement in diverse aspects of childrearing.

Facilitators and barriers also vary across countries. In Cameroon, the Central African Republic, and the Democratic Republic of Congo, child gender is significantly associated with overall paternal involvement. In DR Congo, formal marriage increases fathers' engagement; in Cameroon and DR Congo, fathers with upper secondary education are more involved. In Chad, maternal attitudes and beliefs significantly affect paternal involvement, while in Cameroon, the number of children and fathers' age are negatively associated with overall parenting participation.

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Appendix

Figure A1. Ecological model of favourable and non-favourable conditions for fathers' involvement in children's upbringing. *Source:* Turcotte and Gaudet (2009)

Table A1. Characteristics of the father, his family and children

Indicator	Country/region of residence					
	Cameroon	CAR	Congo	DR Congo	Chad	Central Africa
<i>Gender of the child</i>						
Girl	50.16%	50.00%	46.96%	51.81%	50.06%	50.04%
Boy	49.84%	50.00%	53.04%	48.19%	49.94%	49.96%
<i>Age of the child participating in the study</i>						
3	47.26%	49.61%	48.15%	51.02%	48.27%	49.03%
4	52.74%	50.39%	51.85%	48.98%	51.73%	50.97%
<i>Type of partnership</i>						
Unofficial marriage	27.42%	88.31%	55.95%	9.53%	0.81%	28.07%
Official marriage	72.58%	11.69%	44.05%	90.47%	99.19%	72.03%
<i>Number of wives</i>						
One	82.26%	79.61%	84.13%	84.57%	76.89%	80.99%
Two or more	17.74%	20.39%	15.87%	15.43%	23.11%	19.01%
<i>Level of education</i>						
Primary/no education	53.55%	65.32%	26.98%	31.81%	79.86%	54.31%
Secondary	27.90%	23.25%	46.03%	15.75%	10.16%	21.15%
Higher than secondary	18.55%	11.43%	26.98%	52.44%	9.98%	24.53%
<i>Mothers' views and beliefs</i>						
Traditional	66.94%	43.64%	51.19%	48.58%	35.87%	46.40%
Unconventional	33.06%	56.36%	48.81%	51.42%	64.13%	53.60%
<i>Views and beliefs of fathers</i>						
Traditional	77.10%	72.99%	72.88%	65.43%	64.87%	68.97%
Unconventional	62.90%	27.01%	27.12%	34.57%	35.13%	31.03%
<i>Number of children in the father's household</i>						
1-2	28.23%	22.34%	34.79%	20.79%	18.71%	23.38%
3-4	41.94%	41.30%	43.12%	42.28%	36.00%	40.20%
5 or more	29.84%	36.36%	22.09%	36.93%	45.29%	36.42%
<i>Father's age</i>						
15-29	12.26%	21.17%	16.80%	15.98%	13.88%	15.77%
30-39	53.23%	47.66%	49.21%	52.44%	46.78%	49.50%
40-49	34.52%	31.17%	33.99%	31.57%	39.34%	34.73%
<i>Age difference between spouses</i>						
Less than 5 years	31.94%	40.91%	44.58%	43.46%	23.42%	35.39%
5-9 years	38.89%	35.84%	34.94%	40.47%	41.26%	39.44%
10 years and more	29.19%	23.25%	17.46%	16.06%	35.32%	25.17%
<i>Financial instability</i>						
Yes	42.58%	44.58%	57.86%	60.55%	47.15%	52.70%
No	57.42%	55.32%	32.14%	39.45%	52.85%	47.30%
Number of observations	620	770	756	1270	1614	5030

Source: calculated by the author based on MICS survey data

Table A2. Fathers' involvement in child rearing in Central Africa: logistic regression results

Favourable and hindering factors	Father's involvement in developing development		
	Cognitive	Socio-emotional	Upbringing in general
<i>Country of Residence (ref.: Cameroon)</i>			
CAR	1.73***	0.93 (ns)	1.07 (ns)
Congo	1.76***	1.59***	1.49***
DR Congo	0.93 (ns)	1.00 (ns)	0.98 (ns)
Chad	1.52***	0.90 (ns)	1.10 (ns)
<i>Gender of the child (ref.: girl)</i>			
Boy	1.13*	1.36***	1.30***
<i>Type of partnership (ref.: Informal marriage)</i>			
Official marriage	1.60***	1.21**	1.30***
<i>Number of wives (ref.: one)</i>			
Two or more	0.81**	0.90 (ns)	0.81***
<i>Level of education (ref.: secondary)</i>			
Primary/no education	0.75***	0.82**	0.82**
Higher than secondary	1.43***	1.12 (ns)	1.31***
<i>Views and beliefs of fathers (ref.: traditional)</i>			
Unconventional	1.12*	1.11 (ns)	1.15**
<i>Mothers' views and beliefs (ref.: traditional)</i>			
Unconventional	1.12*	1.14 **	1.15**
<i>Number of children in father's household (ref.: 1-2)</i>			
3-4	0.99 (ns)	0.78***	0.86*
5 or more	1.03 (ns)	0.73***	0.86*
<i>Father's age (ref.: 15-29)</i>			
30-39	0.89 (ns)	1.08 (ns)	1.11 (ns)
40-49	0.82*	0.99 (ns)	0.93 (ns)
<i>Age of the child (ref.: 3 years)</i>			
4 года	1.15**	0.97 (ns)	1.02 (ns)
<i>Age difference between spouses (ref.: 5-9 years)</i>			
Less than 5 years	0.96 (ns)	0.92 (ns)	0.97 (ns)
10 years and more	0.90 (ns)	0.96 (ns)	0.92 (ns)
<i>Financial instability (ref.: none)</i>			
Yes	1.00 (ns)	1.05 (ns)	0.95 (ns)
Coefficient	0.36	0.48	0.92
Predictive ability of the model	73.6%	64.6%	57.6%

Source: calculated by the author based on MICS survey data

Table A3. Fathers’ involvement in child rearing in selected Central African countries: logistic regression results

Favourable and hindering factors	Country/region of residence					Central Africa
	Cameroon	CAR	Congo	DR Congo	Chad	
<i>Gender of the child (ref.: girl)</i>						
Boy	1.40**	1.52***	1.28*	1.33**	1.20*	1.31**
<i>Type of partnership (ref.: Informal marriage)</i>						
Official marriage	1.03 (ns)	1.40 (ns)	1.53**	1.35 (ns)	0.89 (ns)	1.23**
<i>Number of wives (ref.: one)</i>						
Two or more	1.11 (ns)	0.84 (ns)	1.24 (ns)	0.79 (ns)	0.65***	0.82***
<i>Level of education (ref.: secondary)</i>						
Primary/no education	0.83 (ns)	0.69*	0.87 (ns)	1.00 (ns)	0.73*	0.77***
Higher than secondary	2.04***	1.43 (ns)	1.24 (ns)	1.42**	1.08 (ns)	1.14**
<i>Views and beliefs of fathers (ref.: traditional)</i>						
Unconventional	1.11 (ns)	1.37**	1.19 (ns)	1.08 (ns)	1.05 (ns)	1.14**
<i>Mothers’ views and beliefs (ref.: traditional)</i>						
Unconventional	1.06 (ns)	0.88 (ns)	0.97 (ns)	1.11 (ns)	1.34***	1.16**
<i>Number of children in father’s household (ref.: 1-2)</i>						
3-4	0.62**	1.01 (ns)	0.84 (ns)	0.81 (ns)	1.07 (ns)	0.85**
5 or more	0.57**	1.10 (ns)	0.85 (ns)	0.76 (ns)	0.98 (ns)	0.82**
<i>Father’s age (ref.: 15-29)</i>						
30-39	0.65*	1.05 (ns)	1.06 (ns)	1.33 (ns)	1.12 (ns)	1.10 (ns)
40-49	0.45***	0.91 (ns)	1.00 (ns)	1.03 (ns)	1.01 (ns)	0.94 (ns)
<i>Age of the child (ref.: 3 years)</i>						
4 года	0.82 (ns)	1.20 (ns)	1.07 (ns)	0.95 (ns)	1.07 (ns)	1.02 (ns)
<i>Age difference between spouses (ref.: 5-9 years)</i>						
Less than 5 years	0.66*	0.74*	0.90 (ns)	0.91 (ns)	1.27*	0.94 (ns)
10 years and more	0.83 (ns)	1.05 (ns)	0.90 (ns)	0.89 (ns)	1.12 (ns)	0.98 (ns)
<i>Financial instability (ref.: none)</i>						
Yes	1.07 (ns)	1.22 (ns)	1.12 (ns)	1.01 (ns)	0.79**	0.98 (ns)
Coefficient	1.15	0.68	1.22	0.72	1.52	1.03
Predictive ability of the model	63.1%	62.8%	58.2%	56.2%	58.8%	57.0%

Source: calculated by the author based on MICS survey data